

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF *TUNDIKERI* (CHRONIC AND HYPERTROPHIC TONSILS) BY *KSHARAKARMA*- A CASE STUDY**Tamanna Kumari^{1*}, Prof. (Dr.) D. B. Vaghela²**¹PG. Scholar, Dept. of Shalaky Tantra, ITRA, Jamnagar.²HOD, Professor, Dept. of Shalaky Tantra, ITRA, Jamnagar.

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ABSTRACT

Tundikeri is the most common *Kanthagata roga*. It affects due to vitiation of *Kapha*, *Rakta* and involves *Mamsa dusti* at *Hanusandhi* which resembles like *Karpas* (Cotton seed). In classics it is *Shastra sadhya*. Tonsillitis is an inflammation of faucial tonsils caused by viral or bacterial. Acute tonsillitis is managed by antimicrobial medicines. Chronic and hypertrophic tonsils causes Sore throat, difficulty in swallowing food, Fever, Myalgia and Cervical & Jugulodiagastric lymphadynopathy. In this case report a 19 years old female patient presented with gradual onset of throat pain difficulty in swallowing food and associated with right ear discharge and reduced hearing. She was anaemic and on haematinics. Because of anaemia she was not taken for the surgery so consulted to Shalaky OPD and treated with *Ksharakarma*, Oral Medicines and *Gandusha*.

After follow up grade 3 hypertrophy is reduced to grade 1 and symptomatic relief was present.

KEYWORDS: *Tundikeri*, *Ksharakarma*, Tonsilar hypertrophy.

INTRODUCTION

Tundikeri is one such disease where *Acharya sushruta* explained it under *Talugata roga* and *Ashtanga sangraha* described under *Kantharoga*. When common causative factor^[1] are analyzed it shows that derangement of *Kapha*, So *Urdhwajatru roga* manifests due to vitiation of *Kapha dosha*. *Tundikeri* is also manifest due to vitiation of *Kapha* and *Rakta*.

Clinical feature of *Tundikeri* as per *Acharya Sushruta* is *Shopha* (Edema), *Sthula* (Bulky), *Daha* (Burning sensation), *Prapaki* (Inflamed).^[2] After analyzing the description it can be taken as inflamed or acute tonsillitis. As per *Acharya Vagbhata* the swelling resembling like cotton seed (*Karpas Phala*) situated at Temporomandibular joint (*Hanu sandhi*).^[3] Which has mild pain with slimy in nature these correlate merely with Tonsillar hypertrophy or Chronic tonsillitis.

Tonsillitis is often the result of viral or bacterial infection. Symptoms of Acute tonsils are Fever, Tonsil exudates, Sore throat, tender cervical lymphadenopathy along with odynophagia and dysphasia secondary to tonsillar edema. It is managed by antimicrobial treatment and chronic tonsillitis with complications is well managed by Tonsillectomy.

There are some absolute contra- indications even for the surgery those are active infection or acute exacerbation, age below 3years, blood dyscrasias, cervical spine pathology, the patient is on aspirin, oral contraceptive etc, endemic polio, failure to control systemic diseases.^[4] If the patient is having severe tonsillar hypertrophy which is affecting respiration, mental dullness, snoring, and dysphagia because of contraindications we can't neglect and in such cases, the *Kshara Karma* works better way to rid of hypertrophied tonsils.

The treatment of *Tundikeri* is *Shastra sadhya vyadi*^[5] along with this *Kavala*, *Gandusha*, *Pratisarana*, *Nasya* and *Raktamokshana* are explained in classics.

CASE REPORT

Basic Information

Name-XYZ

Age/Gender- 19yrs/ Female

Occupation- Student Socio-economic

Status- Middle

Chief Complaints

Gradual onset of mild throat pain, difficulty in swallowing food and snoring since 3years.

Associated Complaints

Right ear recurrent discharge with pain and generalized weakness since 1year.

History of Present Illness

The patient was apparently healthy before 3yrs gradually she developed throat pain along with difficulty in swallowing food and snoring while sleeping. The Patient was on antimicrobial drugs. After taking medicines pain subsides for time being and after some days same complaints aggravated and also started pain right ear with discharge and gradually reduced hearing in the right ear. Again, patient consulted an ENT surgeon and was advised for Tonsillectomy and Tympanoplasty surgery but due to Anaemia they rejected this case for surgery. On 7.11.2025 came to Shalakya OPD and was hospitalized for further management.

Past History

No/Ho/ DM, Asthma, Tuberculosis K/C/O Anaemia.

Drug History or Medical History- Patient is on Oral Haematinics.

Gynaecological and Obstetrics History

M.H –Regular 3-4/28.

Systemic Examination

CNS-Conscious and Oriented

CVS- S1 and S2+ No Murmur

RS – AEEBS

Local Examination (Oral examination)

Soft palate- Normal Uvula-normal size with no congestion Facial Tonsils- Bilateral Grade 3 Hypertrophy Posterior pharynx - Normal, No post nasal drip.

Table No 1: Grading of the tonsillar hypertrophy.^[6]

Grade 1	Tonsils are congested but are located within the tonsillar fossa
Grade 2	Tonsils hypertrophy is till the brim of the tonsillar fossa
Grade 3	Tonsillar hypertrophy extends beyond the pillars but does not touch each other.
Grade 4	The tonsils are in contact with each other (kissing tonsils)

Table No 2: Ear examination.

	Rt Ear	Lt Ear
EAC	Mucopurulent Discharge+	WNL
Tympanic membrane	Central Perforation+	Intact with Normal cone of light
Rinne's test	BC>AC	AC>BC
Weber Test	Lateralizes	-

Table No 3: Hematological examination.

Hb	4.7 gms%
RBC	3.01millions/uL
PCV	17.9%
MCV	59.5fL
MCH	15.6Pg
MCHC	26.3g/dL
RDW CV	17.3%
Platelet Count	4,39,000/cumm
Peripheral Smear Examination	Hypochromia+,Microcytosis+, Anisocytosis+.

Table No 4: Treatment Given.

Date	Treatment Given	Improvement
7.11.2025	<i>Apamarga Kshara</i> applied to Left tonsil for 100 <i>Matrakala</i> Oral Medicines Cap Grab 1-1-1 A/F Tab <i>Kanchanar Guggulu</i> 2-0-2 A/F <i>Varunadi Kashaya</i> 2tsf-0-2tsf B/F with 2tsf warm water <i>Triphala</i> + <i>Yastimadhu</i> + <i>Tankana Gandusha</i> For 4times day.	-
17.11.2025	<i>Apamarga Kshara</i> applied to RT tonsils for 100 <i>matrakala</i> Same medication continued	The size of left tonsils reduced 80% Mild dysphagia+
28.11.2025	Oral medicines 1) Cap grab 1-1-1 A/F 2) Tab <i>Kanchanar guggulu</i> 2-0-2 A/F 3) <i>Varunadi kashaya</i> 2tsf -0-2tsf B/F with warm water 4) <i>Gandusha</i> is continued	No Dysphagia Voice improvement No ear pain and discharge O/E Bilateral tonsillar hypertrophy is reduced to grade 1. Rt EAC- No discharge. TM-Central perforation+

Figure 1: Before Treatment.**Figure 2: After Treatment.****DISCUSSION**

Tundikeri is one among the *Kanthagata roga* which manifests due to the vitiation of *kapha* and *Rakta dosha* and derangement of *Rasa, rakta* and *mamsa dhatu* at *hanu sandhi* leads to *Karpas phala* (Cotton Seed) resembling growth which presents *Daha, Raga, Prapaka, Picchila* with *Manda ruka* (Mild pain).

As we analyse *samprapti* the *mamsa dusti* is present so *Kshara* is the best choice of treatment in *mansadusti*. *Kshara* possesses *Lekhana, Ropana, Shodhana* and *Shoshana* etc properties^[7] *Apamarga kshara* is *madyama kshara* and appropriate for *pratisarana*.

In this case as patient is suffering from anaemia and anaemia is absolute contraindication for Tonsillectomy surgery. After *kshara* application -tonsils are treated as *vrana* so following medicines are used.

Cap Grab

It is a proprietary medicine contains *vrinapari rasa, Triphala guggulu, Gandhaka rasayana, arogyavardini rasa, Guduchi* and *manjistha*. The main action of this drug is *kandugna* and *lekhana* along with wound healing as it processes anti-inflammatory action. *Tab kanchanar Guggulu*-It pacifies *kapha -vata* and acts on *rasa, rakta, mamsa,* and *medas* and has properties *Lekhana, Kshanana* and *Pachana* so it is explained under *Arbuda, Granthi, Vrana, Bhagandhra, Pakwa vidradi* etc.^[8] *Varunadi Kashaya*- It is *Kapha medohara, agni deepana* and *vidradihara*.^[9] It can be used as effective Ayurvedic formulation to control Chronic inflammatory disorder.^[10] *Gandusha- Triphala* is best anti-inflammatory; *yastimadhu* is *lekhaneeya kantya dravya* so *Gandusha* with this *kashaya* helps to relieve the symptoms early. *Gandusha* is procedure adopted for *mukharoga* where the medicine (*kashaya* or *kalka*) are holded in oral cavity for specific duration^[11] *Triphala* and *yastimadhu* possesses *Kashaya, madhura rasa* so it is given as *ropana gandusha* in this case.

CONCLUSION

Tundikeri is effectively managed by *ksharakarma* without any complications and in conditions like tonsillitis with comorbidities and also some contraindicating factors associated with the disease. *Kshara karma* is effective karma adopted in *kapha* and *vatahara roga* along *mamsa dusti*. In this case, grade 3 hypertrophy is reduced to grade 1 hypertrophy, and symptomatic relief was present without any complications. The medicines which possess

kapha vatahara and *gandusha* alleviate the *dosha* present in the oral cavity thus pacifies the disease.

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